

Self-broadened line parameters for water vapour in the spectral region 5000-5600 cm⁻¹

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Abstract

The self-broadening coefficients and intensities of approximately 460 of the strongest water vapour lines (intensity $S \geq 1.5 \times 10^{-23}$ cm molec⁻¹) in the spectral region 5000 to 5600 cm⁻¹ have been derived from new laboratory measurements. The derived line intensities are on average in a good agreement with those in HITRAN-2001 (v.11.0) (within 0.5% for total band intensity). Self-broadening coefficients are reported for the first time in this spectral region and are compared with values estimated from the HITRAN-2001 foreign-broadening coefficients. Comparison has been also made with the recent HITRAN-2004 (v.12.0) compilation, which revealed marked systematic differences in the self-broadening coefficients (up to 20%) and in the line intensities (up to 5%). The possible reasons for these deviations are discussed.

Keywords: HITRAN database; line parameters fitting; apodization

1. Introduction

The HITRAN database of spectral lines parameters is an important component of many atmospheric and spectroscopic applications [1]. So far it contains parameters of more than 1 million spectral lines and is regularly updated with line parameters derived from new laboratory measurements and theoretical calculations.

In our recent laboratory investigations, devoted to the detection of water dimer in pure vapour samples [2], it was necessary to know the self-broadened halfwidth of the water vapour spectral lines in the spectral region 5000-5600 cm^{-1} . It was found that uncertainty in this parameter impacted significantly on our conclusions. However, self-broadened coefficients of these lines are not catalogued in HITRAN-2001 [1]. The origin of the HITRAN-2001 update of H_2O line parameters in this spectral region is described by Toth [3]. This paper presents the results of deriving these parameters from line fitting to pure water vapour spectra, obtained at the Molecular Spectroscopy Facility at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory using a high-resolution Fourier transform spectrometer.

2. Experimental setup

The Fourier transform measurement used in this work was performed at a path length of 29 cm, temperature 296.8 K and pure water vapour pressure of 20 and 9.4 hPa. The unapodized spectral resolution was 0.0068 cm^{-1} (resolution is defined here as 0.9/maximum-optical-path-difference). The Bruker IFS 120HR Fourier transform spectrometer (FTS) was configured with a 150 W quartz tungsten halogen source, a calcium fluoride beam-splitter, and a liquid nitrogen-cooled indium antimonide (InSb) detector. Mertz phase correction [4] was applied to the measured interferograms. Optical filters were used to limit the optical bandwidth to the spectral range of the measurement.

Water vapour samples were prepared using a clean glass/PTFE vacuum line from distilled liquid water (Analar grade, BDH Chemicals), which had previously been purified to remove dissolved air using at least three repeat 200 K freeze-pump-thaw cycles. Agreement between the humidity sensor and pressure gauge readings (to within the humidity sensor accuracy) confirmed the purity of the water vapour introduced to the gas cells. The vapour pressure, relative humidity and temperature were recorded at 5-second intervals during the measurement on the water vapour sample.

Evacuated-cell background spectra were recorded before and after each filling of the cell. Before each background spectrum was recorded, high-resolution test measurements were made to check that the water vapour had been adequately removed from the gas cell. The

criterion for this was that the intensities of the strongest water vapour lines were reduced to the peak value of the spectral noise in the corresponding spectral region. Taking the ratio of the sample and averaged background spectra minimised errors in the transmittance or absorbance spectra arising from changes in baseline signal level, e.g. due to drifts in the near-IR source intensity.

The r.m.s. signal-to-noise ratio in each of the transmittance spectra exceeded 1000:1 across the entire spectral range of the water vapour absorption features, giving an information-to-noise ratio in excess of 100:1 for absorbances between 0.2 and 3.5. The maximum information-to-noise ratio at an absorbance of around 1.0 was 370:1.

More details concerning these laboratory measurements were reported previously by Smith et al. [5].

3. Fitting procedure

The observed laboratory transmittance spectrum for water vapour pressure 20 and 9.4 hPa and path length 29 cm was compared with calculated spectra, generated for the measured laboratory conditions using the HITRAN-2001 update of the water vapour spectral lines and the line-by-line code of Mitsel et al. [6]. The code of Dudhia [7] was also used for reference line-by-line calculations.

Information about the optical configuration of the FTS was used to calculate an instrument line shape (ILS) and convolute it with the calculated molecular spectrum. The initial ILS was determined from the ideal ‘sinc’ function:

$$ILS_o(w) = 2L_{max} \text{ sinc}(2L_{max}(w-w_o)),$$

where $L_{max}=132$ cm is the maximum optical path difference, and $w_o=5300$ cm^{-1} is the wavenumber of the band centre. Then the $ILS_o(w)$ was convoluted with a boxcar field-of-view (FOV) function to account for the finite FOV of the spectrometer (i.e. the effect of off-axis rays passing through the aperture) [8]. This leads to the broadening of the final ILS function and a shift to lower wavenumber by an amount equal to the half-width of the FOV function (Fig. 1).

Initially Norton-Beer weak apodization [9] was also applied to all of the measured interferograms and to the ILS function being convoluted with the numerical spectrum. However, it was found that the apodization leads to an underestimation of the fitted intensities of the strongest lines that were approaching saturation in our measurements (optical depth ≥ 3). The underestimation was found to increase with line strength growth (see Fig. 4(c)). To

ensure that this deviation had an artificial nature, an intercomparison was made with intensities derived from fitting to an air broadened measurement. We could not ascertain the exact reason of this effect and decided to use unapodized interferograms and ILS function, which removed the effect completely. The use of unapodized spectra is advocated, for example, in [8] on the basis of the fact that apodization introduces an artificial weighting of the interferogram data and leads to a decrease of resolution. However, the undamped ringing (sidelobes) inherent in unapodized ILS function necessitates the use of rather far ILS wings to convolute with numerical spectrum, which in its turn impact the time of the fitting procedure. The optimal distance at which the ILS can be truncated without significant loss in the accuracy of retrieved line parameters has been derived and checked carefully by fitting to synthetic spectra.

We used the Levenberg-Marquardt least square algorithm to fit the parameters for about 500 of the strongest lines ($S \geq 1.5 \times 10^{-23}$ cm molec⁻¹) in the spectral region 5000-5600cm⁻¹. Four parameters: line centre position, intensity, self-broadening halfwidth γ_{self} , and baseline, were fitted for each spectral line using Voigt profile in the first stage (with the Doppler halfwidth calculated for each line). Then the fifth, narrowing parameter β , was added to the fitting procedure to account for the collisional narrowing effect (Dicke-effect) [10]. The Rautian-Sobelman profile describing strong collision model [11] was used for the fitting procedure in the second stage according to the Varghese and Hanson description [12]. The average value of the pressure independent dimensionless collisional narrowing parameter $\beta/\gamma_{\text{self}}$ was found to be about 0.15 (with standard deviation ~ 0.15) and weakly affected the retrieved line intensities and self-broadening coefficients for most of lines. Not accounting for the collisional narrowing (i.e., fitting with the Voigt profile) led, on average, to underestimation of the fitted line intensities and self-broadening widths by about 0.5-1.5% and 2-5% respectively.

Spectral lines were fitted simultaneously in sets of 5-10 lines. The fitting procedure for the whole spectral region was repeated several times until total residual between two consecutive iterations became less than some given small value. Every line was fitted within $10 \cdot \gamma_v$ spectral interval from the line centre, where γ_v is an average Voigt halfwidth (HWHM) of the spectral line for the measurement ($\gamma_v \sim 0.01$ cm⁻¹). According to the results of numerical simulations described in [13] fitting over less than a $7\gamma_v$ -interval may lead, in certain conditions, to strong growth in the errors of retrieved line parameters. The impact of unfitted

spectral lines ($S < 0.7 \times 10^{-23}$ cm molec⁻¹) was taken into account according their parameters in HITRAN database.

We want to underline the necessity of including a *baseline for each line* in the list of fitted parameters. It is especially important in cases where significant smooth absorption, for example, the water vapour continuum, is expected. Otherwise the continuum absorption will be partly or entirely ‘included’ by fitting procedure in retrieved intensities and halfwidths of the weak spectral lines, causing their overestimation. This effect is shown in Figure 2, where results of retrieval of line intensities and self-broadening coefficients from fitting to a synthetic spectrum is presented for the cases when a baseline for each line is included (Fig. 2a) and not included (Fig. 2b) in the list of fitted parameters. The synthetic spectrum was calculated for the measurement conditions (20 hPa pure water vapour, 29 cm path length) and spectral region 5000-5600 cm⁻¹ with CKD-2.4 continuum [14] included in the calculation as an example. The overestimation of the retrieved parameters grows noticeably for the weaker lines, reaching 10% for the line intensities and more than 15% for self-broadening coefficients. The relations of the fitted values to those of the synthetic spectrum are very near unity for all spectral lines when their baselines are included in the fitting procedure (Fig. 2b). This effect should be still more pronounced for the spectra obtained in atmospheric conditions, because of the bigger contribution of the air-broadened continuum absorption compared to the low-pressure pure water case.

The first guesses for the line parameters in the fitting procedure were taken directly from the HITRAN-2001 database. The initial approximation for self-broadening halfwidths was calculated using the approximation $\gamma_{\text{self}} = 5 \cdot \gamma_{\text{air}}^0 \cdot P$, where γ_{air}^0 is the corresponding HITRAN air-broadening coefficient and P is the water vapour pressure. A similar approximation is used by most line-by-line codes when information about H₂O self-broadening coefficient is not available from HITRAN.

During the fitting procedure only those parts of the spectrum with an optical depth of less than 4.0 were used, to minimise the impact of saturated spectral intervals. Possible errors in line parameter retrieval, caused by excluding some saturated central part of the line profile from the fitting, were investigated for example in [13]. On the other hand, the saturated lines (optical depth up to 8-12) were also a good indicator of accuracy of the derived ILS. It is known that ILS-induced line strength errors are strongly enhanced for the lines with high opacity [8]. Artificial narrowing or broadening of our ILS by 20-50%, to check the impact of

ILS errors, led to a deviation in the fitted intensities of the strongest lines similar to that already described for the apodized ILS (see the Fig. 4(c))¹. The retrieved intensities of the weaker lines, however, remain mostly insensitive to variation in the width of the ILS. This can be explained by combination of three factors: a) the width of the ILS is smaller than the average line width of the monochromatic spectrum (0.007-0.012 cm⁻¹ compared to ~0.02 cm⁻¹ respectively); b) the area under a spectral feature is not influenced by ILS errors (assuming normalised ILS area); c) absorption and optical depth are approximately equal for the optically thin lines.

Comment:

4. Results and discussion

HITRAN-2001 (v.11.0)

Some examples of the measured and fitted spectra are presented in the Fig. 3. For a number of weak lines the fitted intensities and self-broadening coefficients are a factor 2-3 different from the corresponding values in the HITRAN-2001 database. However, in most cases there was found to be a good agreement between fitted parameters and those in HITRAN-2001. Figures 4 and 5 show comparisons of the fitted and HITRAN-2001 line intensities and broadening coefficients respectively, in the spectral region under investigation. Figure 4 panel (a) shows the distribution of line intensities as a function of wavenumber. In figures 4 and 5 the ratios of fitted and HITRAN-2001 line parameters are shown in panel (b) as a function of wavenumber and in (c) as a function of line intensity. Panel (a) in figure 5 demonstrates fitted self-broadening coefficients and $5\gamma_{\text{air}}^0$ parameters from HITRAN-2001 versus an energy-ordered index $J''(J''+1)+Ka''-Kc''+1$ as defined in [15], where J'' , Ka'' and Kc'' are rotational quantum numbers of lower energy level.

In general, there is good agreement between fitted and HITRAN line strengths. The total band intensity (or band-averaged intensity) is ~0.3% larger than that calculated from HITRAN-2001; the standard deviation of line intensities from the average value is ~6%. There is also relatively good agreement between the fitted self-broadening coefficients and those calculated using the $5\cdot\gamma_{\text{air}}^0$ approximation. The average $\gamma_{\text{self}}^0/5\gamma_{\text{air}}^0$ value is 1.09 and the standard deviation is about 30%.

¹ As was mentioned above, the reference values for the intensities of the strongest lines (saturated in our pure water measurements) were obtained from the independent air-broadened measurements, where the impact of the ILS errors was negligible because of much wider spectral features compared to the ILS width.

The error bars in Figures 4 and 5 include both the estimated error from the measurement and the uncertainty from the fitting procedure. However, the real errors may be larger if there were some unrecognised sources of uncertainty. Such uncertainties may have in part been included in the error bars, since line parameters were derived by fitting to measurements at two different water vapour pressures: 20 and 9.4 hPa. The higher priority, however, was given to the results of the higher-pressure measurement because of smaller impact of Doppler broadening on the total line width compared to the self-broadening.

HITRAN-2004 (v.12.0)

During the preparation of this paper, the new HITRAN compilation - HITRAN-2004 (or v.12.0) was enounced by Rothman et al. [16]. The first preliminary results, obtained with this new version of HITRAN by different authors, have shown that significant improvements had been made compared to the previous HITRAN update with respect to the both new spectral lines and improvement of accuracy in the former line parameters. Analyzing the new HITRAN database we found that self-broadening coefficients in the spectral region under consideration have appeared in HITRAN-2004.

The fitting procedure, described above, was repeated using the HITRAN-2004 line parameters as the first guess instead of those from HITRAN-2001. Line intensities and self-broadening coefficients derived in this approach are mostly in a very good agreement with those retrieved using HITRAN-2001 as an initial guess. This confirms the good convergence of the developed fitting algorithm in search of global minimum, especially, taking into consideration the rather marked difference we found between the line parameters in HITRAN-2004 and HITRAN-2001.

Figures 6 and 7 are equivalent to Figs. 4 and 5 but using HITRAN-2004 instead of HITRAN-2001. It can be seen from Fig. 6 that our fitted intensities are systematically below than those in HITRAN-2004. The systematic deviation changes gradually from 6% for the weak lines to close to zero for the strong ones.

The much lower random spread in respect to our data can be noted for HITRAN-2004 self-broadening coefficients, compared to HITRAN-2001 (compare Fig. 7(c) with Fig 5(c)). However, again there is marked systematic disagreement between HITRAN-2004 and our self-broadening parameters. In contrast to the line intensities, where maximum disagreement is observed for the weakest lines, the deviation between HITRAN-2004 and fitted self-broadening coefficients increases in the direction of the stronger lines and reaches a maximum for the lines with intensities about $5 \cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹ (see Fig. 7(c)).

The error code attributed to the most HITRAN-2004 line intensities under comparison is '5', which corresponds to the relative error 5-10%. The same retrieval accuracy on average can be attributed to our line intensities. It means that the difference between HITRAN-2004 and our line intensities lies within error level. For the self-broadening coefficient, however, the error code for many lines corresponds to the relative error 5-10% and, therefore, can not explain up to 20% disagreement with our data.

It is difficult to give any definite explanation to these deviations. However, the possible reason for the sharp fall (from 20% to zero) of the systematic deviation between our and HITRAN-2004 self-broadening coefficients in the region of line intensities near $5\text{-}6\cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹ (Fig. 7(c)) can be that the coefficients have different reference indices in HITRAN-2004. The coefficients for the most lines with intensity below $6\cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹ cite the work of Toth [17], whereas coefficients for the lines with intensity above $5\cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹ are cited in HITRAN-2004 reference file having been obtained as the "smoothed values" from Toth [17]. These works, cited in HITRAN-2004, are not published under the mentioned titles and most probably they correspond to the papers of Toth [18-19] which have appeared recently. If this is the case, then the self-broadening coefficients of the weaker lines ($< 6\cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹) described above were derived in [19] by direct fit to the measured spectra. The self-broadening coefficients for the strongest lines in this band ($> 5\cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹) were obtained in [18] by fitting the measured values by an empirically derived 'smoothing function' for each 'family' of rotational transitions. Hence, the smoothed self-broadening values of the strongest lines, derived in [18], are rather close to our fitted values, while the 'measured' values of the weaker lines (obtained in [19]) show marked systematic overestimation compared to our data.

It is not clear from the description given in [19], whether the baseline for each spectral line was taken into account during the fitting of line intensities and self-broadening widths to the measured spectra. As was shown above (see Fig. 2), this factor can markedly affect retrieved parameters for relatively weak lines. In our recent work [2] we found considerable extra-continuum absorption in the spectral region $5200\text{-}5450$ cm⁻¹ which we attributed to water dimers. It means that one should be very cautious about accounting for the local baseline contribution when fitting the spectral line parameters in this spectral region. Otherwise the dimers feature could be partly implicitly 'included' in the retrieved intensities and self-broadening coefficients of the weak lines causing their overestimation.

It should be mentioned also that the Galatry profile used in [18] to fit the measured spectral lines is obtained from the soft-collision model [20], which does not correspond to the

case of H₂O – H₂O (or H₂O – N₂) collisions. The Rautian-Sobelman (RS) profile [11], derived within the hard collision model, seems more appropriate for this case. Both models give usually the same good fit to the observed spectra; however the narrowing parameter derived with the soft-collision model is always greater than that for the hard-collision model [21]. This, in its turn, may lead to some overestimation of the derived pressure-broadened line widths when applying the Galatry profile for the hard collision cases.

Figure 8 demonstrates a few fragments of the experimental and calculated transmittance spectra for those lines where the 20% difference in self-broadening coefficient between HITRAN-2004 and our fitting was found. (The ILS described in the previous section was used for both calculated spectra) It can be seen that this overestimation of self-broadening in HITRAN leads to the noticeable difference between experimental pure water vapour spectrum and that calculated using HITRAN-2004.

The intensities and self-broadening coefficients of 464 spectral lines derived in this work are presented in Table 1 together with their estimated errors. The line parameters derived here at 296.8 K were converted to the temperature 296 K according to the usual relations:

$$S(T_2) = S(T_1) (T_1/T_2)^{3/2} \exp\{-E''(hc/k)(1/T_2 - 1/T_1)\};$$

$$\gamma_{\text{self}}^0(T_2) = (T_1/T_2)^n \gamma_{\text{self}}^0(T_1);$$

where E'' is the lower state energy of the transition in cm^{-1} ; n is the line width temperature dependence, which assumed here to be equal to that presented in HITRAN for the air width. The $S(T_1)$ and $S(T_2)$ are both in $\text{cm}\cdot\text{molec}^{-1}$ here. The HITRAN-format file with the parameters is also attached as Supplementary Material. The line centre wavenumbers in the Table are taken from HITRAN-2004, since no simultaneous multi-pressure fitting was performed to account for possible pressure shifts. Information about the intensity and self-broadening errors from this work has also been included in the HITRAN-format file using the HITRAN accuracy indices.

5. Summary and conclusions

We have derived self-broadening coefficients and intensities of 464 of the strongest water vapour lines ($S \geq 1.5 \times 10^{-23} \text{ cm molec}^{-1}$) from new laboratory measurements on pure water vapour in the spectral region 5000 to 5600 cm^{-1} . The derived line intensities are on average in a good agreement with those in HITRAN-2001 (within 0.5% for the band-averaged intensity and a standard deviation of 6% for line intensities). Self-broadening coefficients are reported for the first time in this spectral region and were found to be in a reasonable

agreement with the $5\gamma_{\text{air}}^0$ approximation. The average $\gamma_{\text{self}}^0/5\gamma_{\text{air}}^0$ ratio was 1.09 with a standard deviation 30%.

A different situation was found when comparing our data with HITRAN-2004. The spectral line intensities and self-broadening coefficients in HITRAN-2004, have generally lower random dispersal from our fitted data than in HITRAN-2001, but show, however, a marked systematic overestimation compared to our parameters. The disagreement in intensity reaches 5-6% for the weak lines falling gradually to zero for the strong lines. The deviation in self-broadening coefficients grows from a few percents for weak lines up to ~20% for stronger lines, and falls abruptly to zero for the lines with intensities more than $6 \cdot 10^{-21}$ cm molec⁻¹, which most probably is caused by two different approaches used for the two group of lines in HITRAN-2004. Further investigations are required to clarify this effect.

We underline the importance of accounting for the local baseline contribution when fitting line intensities and halfwidths to the measured spectra in order to avoid the impact of the continuum absorption of the strong lines or the water dimer absorption on the retrieved parameters of the weak lines.

It is worth mentioning that the line intensity ratios Fitted/HITRAN-2001 (Fig. 4(b)) are in reasonable agreement with a scaling factor derived by Smith et al. [5] from the same laboratory data and for the same spectral region. This agreement confirms that the scaling factor method used in [5] whilst crude compared to line fitting, is valid for the initial assessment of spectrally averaged line intensities. Similar line fitting analysis is planned for the other spectral regions (6600 to 7600 cm⁻¹ and 8400 to 9200 cm⁻¹) studied in [5].

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Figure captions

- Figure 1.** ILS function was derived by a convolution of the ‘sinc’ function ($ILS_o(w)$) with boxcar FOV function with the width $w_o(\theta_{FOV})^2/2$. Here $\theta_{FOV} = r/f = 1.4$ mrad, where r is the radius of the aperture and f is the focal length of the collimator.
- Figure 2.** The ratios of the fitted line intensities and self-broadening coefficients to their original values are presented versus line intensity for the case when baselines are included (a) and not included (b) in the fitted parameters. The fitting was performed to the synthetic spectrum (20 hPa pure water vapour, 296K, spectral region 5000-5600 cm^{-1}) with CKD-2.4 continuum absorption included.
- Figure 3.** Comparisons between the measured (dots), HITRAN-2001 (dashed curve) and fitted (solid curve) spectra at (a) 5526 cm^{-1} , (b) 5541 cm^{-1} and (c) 5141 cm^{-1} . The measured spectra are of pure water vapour at 20 hPa, over a path length of 29 cm and at a temperature of 296.8 K.
- Figure 4.** Comparisons of fitted and HITRAN-2001 line intensities in the spectral region 5040 to 5600 cm^{-1} . Panel (a) shows the distribution of line intensities as a function of wavenumber. The ratio of fitted and HITRAN-2001 line intensities are shown in panel (b) as a function of wavenumber and in (c) as a function of line intensity. In panel (c) data is shown for both unapodized and apodized spectra.
- Figure 5.** Comparisons of fitted self-broadening coefficients and HITRAN-2001 $5\gamma_{\text{air}}$ coefficients in the spectral region 5040 to 5600 cm^{-1} . Panel (a) shows the distribution of coefficients as a function of energy ordered index as defined in [12]. The ratio of fitted and HITRAN-2001 $5\gamma_{\text{air}}$ coefficients is shown in panel (b) as a function of wavenumber and in (c) as a function of line intensity.
- Figure 6.** The ratios of fitted and HITRAN-2004 line intensities in the spectral region 5040 to 5600 cm^{-1} are shown as a function of wavenumber (a) and line intensity (b).
- Figure 7.** Comparisons of fitted and HITRAN-2004 self-broadening coefficients in the spectral region 5040 to 5600 cm^{-1} . Panel (a) shows the distribution of coefficients as a function of energy ordered index as defined in [12]. The ratio of fitted and HITRAN-2004 coefficients is shown in panel (b) as a function of wavenumber and in (c) as a function of line intensity. The dashed curve in the panel (c) separates two sets of lines that have different reference indices (see arrows) for self-broadening coefficient in HITRAN-2004.
- Figure 8.** Comparisons between the measured (dots) and calculated spectra using HITRAN-2004 (dashed curve) and fitted parameters (solid curve) are presented near the lines for which a $\sim 20\%$ difference in self-broadening coefficient was found between HITRAN-2004 and our fitting. The measured spectra are of pure water vapour at 20 hPa, over a path length of 29 cm and at a temperature of 296.8 K. The ILS described in section 3 is used in the both calculations.

Table 1. Water vapour line intensities and self-broadening coefficients derived in this work are presented together with their estimated relative errors δ (in %), line center wavenumbers, and quantum numbers. The data is presented for 296 K.

Wavenumber, cm ⁻¹	Intensity, cm molec ⁻¹	δ , %	Self- broadening, cm ⁻¹ atm ⁻¹	δ , %	V'	J' Ka' Kc'	J'' Ka'' Kc''
5042.68486	1.969E-23	10	0.3545	14	011	4 2 2	5 4 1
5049.0087	3.5E-23	7	0.3833	10	011	4 1 4	5 3 3
5049.36628	2.198E-23	10	0.3516	14	011	5 0 5	6 2 4
5049.60747	2.796E-23	8	0.1149	34	011	12 0 12	13 0 13
5050.6944	1.412E-22	5	0.3348	6	110	3 3 0	4 4 1
5051.11764	4.526E-23	7	0.3267	10	110	3 3 1	4 4 0
5061.00515	1.833E-23	7	0.425	11	110	3 1 3	4 2 2
5065.18724	4.626E-23	5	0.3915	8	110	3 2 2	4 3 1
5065.25307	2.228E-23	7	0.2887	11	011	10 3 7	11 3 8
5065.45083	1.794E-23	7	0.4391	10	110	7 0 7	8 1 8
5070.36683	4.942E-23	7	0.4732	12	011	5 1 4	6 3 3
5071.35569	3.169E-23	7	0.1901	17	011	11 2 10	12 2 11
5072.07931	1.501E-22	5	0.4184	7	110	3 2 1	4 3 2
5081.2097	4.766E-23	8	0.4558	13	110	5 1 4	6 2 5
5081.44079	4.639E-23	16	0.3679	14	011	10 2 8	11 2 9
5086.40373	2.772E-23	8	0.407	10	011	9 3 6	10 3 7
5088.06583	3.003E-23	7	0.2605	13	110	6 1 6	7 0 7
5090.62758	5.044E-23	7	0.3983	10	011	3 1 3	4 3 2
5092.3604	9.74E-23	7	0.2214	7	011	10 1 9	11 1 10
5092.79053	3.237E-23	8	0.2456	16	011	10 2 9	11 2 10
5093.32596	2.184E-22	6	0.4334	6	110	2 2 1	3 3 0
5094.71955	7.346E-23	6	0.3911	12	110	2 2 0	3 3 1
5095.09892	4.265E-23	7	0.427	13	110	8 4 5	9 3 6
5096.59946	2.716E-22	6	0.2192	11	011	10 0 10	11 0 11
5096.60285	9.042E-23	6	0.2457	27	011	10 1 10	11 1 11
5099.1247	4.173E-23	7	0.3115	14	011	9 2 7	10 2 8
5099.47347	1.917E-22	5	0.4196	7	011	4 1 3	5 3 2
5103.34369	1.245E-22	5	0.5032	7	110	2 1 2	3 2 1
5104.16049	2.036E-22	5	0.4562	6	011	4 0 4	5 2 3
5105.39945	3.429E-23	8	0.3673	12	110	7 0 7	7 1 6
5106.19486	5.593E-23	5	0.2906	10	011	9 4 6	10 4 7
5107.07009	1.178E-22	5	0.2764	8	011	9 3 7	10 3 8
5107.58184	6.894E-23	6	0.3837	9	110	5 0 5	6 1 6
5109.18487	1.335E-22	5	0.4856	7	110	3 1 2	4 2 3
5109.98793	2.275E-23	9	0.4033	16	110	5 1 5	6 0 6
5111.32511	2.068E-22	4	0.3811	6	011	8 3 5	9 3 6
5113.00453	9.328E-23	4	0.2747	7	011	9 1 8	10 1 9
5113.8696	2.697E-22	4	0.2547	6	011	9 2 8	10 2 9
5114.48658	2.55E-23	9	0.3131	16	011	9 5 5	10 5 6
5116.79517	3.694E-22	4	0.3571	6	011	8 2 6	9 2 7
5119.41628	2.284E-22	4	0.2603	6	011	9 0 9	10 0 10
5119.45521	6.845E-22	4	0.2473	6	011	9 1 9	10 1 10
5119.65692	1.39E-22	5	0.3573	8	011	8 4 4	9 4 5
5121.39799	6.368E-23	7	0.4423	11	110	6 1 6	6 2 5
5122.46867	5.271E-23	6	0.4239	11	011	3 1 2	4 3 1
5125.70905	6.056E-23	6	0.4258	9	110	2 1 1	3 2 2
5126.94463	4.278E-23	8	0.4478	10	110	4 0 4	5 1 5
5128.30737	1.013E-22	5	0.2764	8	011	8 3 6	9 3 7
5129.6781	1.503E-22	5	0.3992	7	011	7 3 4	8 3 5
5130.28044	5.074E-23	7	0.2915	16	011	8 4 5	9 4 6
5130.55263	2.005E-23	13	0.4118	28	110	6 0 6	6 1 5
5132.02173	1.049E-22	6	0.4467	9	110	4 1 4	5 0 5
5132.95977	6.686E-22	5	0.2865	5	011	8 1 7	9 1 8
5134.77711	2.187E-22	5	0.2675	8	011	8 2 7	9 2 8
5135.72234	3.202E-22	4	0.402	6	011	7 2 5	8 2 6
5137.99386	7.329E-23	6	0.5134	10	110	1 1 1	2 2 0
5138.67159	7.329E-23	9	0.3641	7	011	8 5 3	9 5 4
5139.32147	3.742E-23	8	0.4669	14	011	5 2 4	5 4 1
5140.28325	2.48E-23	9	0.3013	23	011	8 5 4	9 5 5
5140.47579	3.407E-23	13	0.4269	26	110	5 1 5	5 2 4
5141.07664	2.986E-23	13	0.3356	32	110	6 3 4	6 4 3
5141.53208	5.311E-23	10	0.4082	19	110	6 2 5	6 3 4
5141.75082	1.594E-21	5	0.2981	5	011	8 0 8	9 0 9
5141.8301	5.325E-22	5	0.2913	7	011	8 1 8	9 1 9
5142.75321	8.275E-23	6	0.4732	9	011	2 1 1	3 3 0
5143.20332	6.766E-23	6	0.3473	10	110	7 4 4	8 3 5
5144.76941	2.304E-22	5	0.4927	6	110	1 1 0	2 2 1
5144.85362	1.932E-22	5	0.552	7	110	3 0 3	4 1 4
5146.90634	3.457E-23	9	0.3848	19	110	4 3 2	4 4 1
5149.45794	1.162E-22	5	0.3648	9	011	7 4 3	8 4 4
5150.38647	7.372E-22	4	0.3021	6	011	7 3 5	8 3 6
5150.85459	1.397E-22	5	0.4504	7	011	3 0 3	4 2 2
5151.82891	2.689E-23	9	0.3882	18	110	5 2 4	5 3 3
5152.09904	5.218E-22	4	0.3676	6	011	7 1 6	8 1 7
5154.62726	4.362E-23	7	0.4966	11	110	7 1 6	7 2 5
5154.73193	4.717E-23	7	0.4525	9	110	3 1 3	4 0 4

5154.92549	3.346E-23	7	0.2819	11	011	9	1	9	9	1	8
5155.15441	3.625E-22	4	0.2925	5	011	7	4	4	8	4	5
5155.37668	1.146E-22	4	0.4708	5	110	5	0	5	5	1	4
5155.47098	1.499E-21	4	0.304	5	011	7	2	6	8	2	7
5156.92642	2.239E-21	4	0.4092	5	011	6	2	4	7	2	5
5159.14661	9.575E-23	14	0.3736	31	110	4	2	3	4	3	2
5159.9341	1.318E-21	5	0.3973	7	011	6	3	3	7	3	4
5161.72777	8.007E-23	17	0.4343	34	110	2	0	2	3	1	3
5163.57243	1.091E-21	4	0.3401	7	011	7	0	7	8	0	8
5163.75277	3.272E-21	4	0.3377	6	011	7	1	7	8	1	8
5165.62786	5.059E-23	6	0.3139	11	011	7	5	2	8	5	3
5166.19303	1.522E-22	5	0.2722	7	011	7	5	3	8	5	4
5169.13428	3.518E-23	9	0.5289	12	011	4	1	4	4	3	1
5169.17762	9.001E-23	9	0.4098	17	110	3	2	1	3	3	0
5170.53231	3.25E-21	4	0.4034	5	011	6	1	5	7	1	6
5173.48543	5.111E-22	5	0.3297	8	011	6	3	4	7	3	5
5174.01795	2.939E-23	11	0.5076	19	110	6	1	5	6	2	4
5176.12719	9.661E-22	4	0.3501	6	011	6	2	5	7	2	6
5176.31896	8.735E-23	6	0.3445	11	011	8	0	8	8	2	7
5177.36801	8.054E-23	7	0.3991	12	110	5	2	3	5	3	2
5178.09904	7.021E-22	4	0.3369	6	011	6	4	2	7	4	3
5178.3571	4.611E-23	7	0.1809	22	011	7	6	2	8	6	3
5178.7384	1.362E-22	6	0.4655	9	110	2	1	2	3	0	3
5178.90291	2.394E-22	7	0.4279	11	110	1	0	1	2	1	2
5180.18935	1.407E-22	8	0.4058	16	110	6	4	3	7	3	4
5180.57031	2.465E-22	6	0.2845	13	011	6	4	3	7	4	4
5180.62949	1.437E-21	4	0.3998	6	011	5	2	3	6	2	4
5184.83051	6.069E-21	4	0.3714	6	011	6	0	6	7	0	7
5185.23705	2.019E-21	4	0.3637	6	011	6	1	6	7	1	7
5186.11371*	1.78E-23	7	0.3417	11	011	5	1	5	6	1	6
5187.24833	3.653E-23	5	0.3478	8	110	7	4	3	8	3	6
5187.61041	1.561E-22	4	0.4268	5	110	5	1	4	5	2	3
5188.37437*	1.905E-23	7	0.3947	10	011	4	1	3	5	1	4
5188.50336	1.339E-22	7	0.3625	12	110	4	3	2	5	2	3
5188.58039	5.317E-22	5	0.4316	7	011	2	0	2	3	2	1
5189.00996	2.018E-21	4	0.4347	5	011	5	1	4	6	1	5
5189.71955	8.633E-22	4	0.3856	6	011	5	3	2	6	3	3
5191.87895	2.701E-22	5	0.266	6	011	6	5	1	7	5	2
5192.03535	9.017E-23	5	0.2656	11	011	6	5	2	7	5	3
5195.14014	8.118E-23	6	0.4979	10	110	4	1	3	4	2	2
5195.84656	5.672E-23	7	0.3836	12	110	2	1	1	2	2	0
5196.3262	3.081E-22	6	0.4805	9	110	3	0	3	3	1	2
5196.75124	4.605E-21	4	0.4119	5	011	5	2	4	6	2	5
5197.39079	2.571E-22	6	0.4038	11	110	3	1	2	3	2	1
5197.53296	2.744E-21	4	0.3607	6	011	5	3	3	6	3	4
5197.83771	6.747E-23	6	0.4787	9	110	0	0	0	1	1	1
5198.02787	6.518E-23	5	0.3653	7	011	7	0	7	7	2	6
5200.71134	4.325E-23	7	0.3973	11	110	6	3	3	7	2	6
5202.24987	2.108E-23	9	0.3912	18	110	7	3	4	8	2	7
5203.70139	2.018E-22	4	0.3794	6	011	7	1	7	7	1	6
5204.06697	2.961E-23	19	0.3995	42	110	1	1	1	2	0	2
5205.03902*	2.989E-23	19	0.4285	41	011	4	0	4	5	0	5
5205.40386	3.876E-22	4	0.3176	7	011	5	4	1	6	4	2
5205.44318	3.372E-21	4	0.4127	5	011	5	0	5	6	0	6
5205.92341	6.347E-23	10	0.329	25	011	8	1	7	8	3	6
5206.23878	1.163E-21	4	0.2729	7	011	5	4	2	6	4	3
5206.31136	1.001E-20	4	0.4165	6	011	5	1	5	6	1	6
5206.51535	7.378E-21	4	0.3733	5	011	4	2	2	5	2	3
5208.11742	8.318E-22	4	0.4115	5	110	5	3	2	6	2	5
5208.82801	1.039E-20	4	0.4221	5	011	4	1	3	5	1	4
5209.26621	2.101E-23	8	0.4367	9	021**	2	0	2	3	0	3
5215.77799	3.536E-23	10	0.3305	24	110	5	4	2	6	3	3
5216.02755	3.28E-22	5	0.4556	7	110	1	0	1	1	1	0
5217.18298	1.357E-21	4	0.4105	6	011	4	2	3	5	2	4
5217.66724	1.104E-22	5	0.2465	10	011	5	5	0	6	5	1
5217.69802	3.303E-22	5	0.2432	8	011	5	5	1	6	5	2
5218.16267	3.818E-22	5	0.3938	8	011	6	0	6	6	2	5
5218.29513	3.853E-23	16	0.3387	41	011	7	1	6	7	3	5
5218.75861	3.901E-21	4	0.3859	5	011	4	3	1	5	3	2
5222.28676	1.325E-21	4	0.3646	6	011	4	3	2	5	3	3
5223.47227	9.946E-23	10	0.3323	22	110	3	3	1	4	2	2
5223.52182	1.401E-21	5	0.4073	6	110	4	3	1	5	2	4
5225.32326	1.527E-20	5	0.473	7	011	4	0	4	5	0	5
5225.76766	1.969E-22	7	0.4154	12	011	6	1	5	6	3	4
5226.35133	3.888E-21	4	0.4568	5	011	4	1	4	5	1	5
5227.84978*	3.399E-23	18	0.3793	42	011	3	1	3	4	1	4
5227.94764	6.948E-23	9	0.3643	19	011	5	1	4	5	3	3
5228.41419	8.61E-23	8	0.3239	18	110	5	4	1	6	3	4
5228.81046	1.401E-22	7	0.3885	12	011	6	1	6	6	1	5
5229.75781	9.361E-23	9	0.4476	15	110	3	2	1	4	1	4
5230.81414	4.898E-21	4	0.4371	5	011	3	1	2	4	1	3
5231.22592	1.056E-21	4	0.4411	6	110	4	2	2	5	1	5
5231.68671	1.298E-21	5	0.3006	6	011	4	4	0	5	4	1
5231.88758	4.34E-22	5	0.2882	8	011	4	4	1	5	4	2
5232.25083	2.798E-23	19	0.3595	48	011	8	2	7	8	2	6
5233.92189	3.137E-21	4	0.3926	5	011	3	2	1	4	2	2
5235.93104	2.205E-22	5	0.4099	8	011	5	0	5	5	2	4

5238.43981	1.845E-21	4	0.4066	5	110	3	3	0	4	2	3
5238.92771	5.855E-23	14	0.4726	26	110	5	2	3	6	1	6
5243.43073*	4.209E-23	17	0.4044	36	011	2	0	2	3	0	3
5243.88627	8.509E-21	4	0.4193	5	011	3	2	2	4	2	3
5244.58137	6.496E-21	7	0.4986	5	011	3	0	3	4	0	4
5246.29999	1.327E-21	4	0.3757	6	011	3	3	0	4	3	1
5247.42618	3.953E-21	4	0.3678	6	011	3	3	1	4	3	2
5247.8464	5.999E-23	36	0.2997	21	110	4	4	1	5	3	2
5248.30608	1.863E-20	7	0.4698	8	011	3	1	3	4	1	4
5250.30888	9.235E-22	5	0.4461	7	011	4	0	4	4	2	3
5254.1062	8.703E-22	5	0.4492	7	011	5	1	5	5	1	4
5254.80598	1.674E-20	5	0.4332	6	011	2	1	1	3	1	2
5255.8767	2.729E-22	6	0.4465	10	110	1	1	0	1	0	1
5258.66137	2.415E-22	6	0.4161	11	011	7	2	6	7	2	5
5260.3327	2.954E-22	6	0.4707	10	011	3	0	3	3	2	2
5261.4997	8.826E-21	4	0.4345	5	011	2	2	0	3	2	1
5261.91967	9.879E-23	10	0.411	19	110	2	1	1	2	0	2
5263.9751	2.247E-20	5	0.4698	6	011	2	0	2	3	0	3
5265.83511	4.337E-22	5	0.472	8	011	2	0	2	2	2	1
5266.04948	3.003E-21	4	0.4312	6	011	2	2	1	3	2	2
5266.86913	6.477E-23	5	0.4955	5	110	2	0	2	1	1	1
5269.13262	6.728E-21	4	0.4753	5	011	2	1	2	3	1	3
5269.57768*	2.559E-23	8	0.4189	7	011	1	1	1	2	1	2
5270.27923	2.515E-23	7	0.3074	8	011	9	3	7	9	3	6
5272.7855	2.093E-22	5	0.4832	7	110	3	1	2	3	0	3
5274.15777	7.62E-23	6	0.441	9	110	1	1	1	0	0	0
5274.64551	3.593E-23	8	0.4422	14	110	3	1	2	2	2	1
5277.47975	3.438E-22	4	0.4697	6	011	4	1	4	4	1	3
5280.1874	4.693E-21	4	0.4093	5	011	1	1	0	2	1	1
5281.23039	7E-23	11	0.4388	20	110	3	2	1	3	1	2
5282.35435	3.089E-22	6	0.4365	9	110	4	2	2	4	1	3
5282.96191	2.153E-22	4	0.4851	5	011	6	2	5	6	2	4
5284.78006	7E-21	4	0.417	5	011	1	0	1	2	0	2
5286.24379	1.958E-23	7	0.3606	11	021**	2	2	0	2	2	1
5286.72255	1.439E-22	4	0.4739	5	110	5	2	3	5	1	4
5288.86692	3.5E-23	7	0.3851	10	110	4	1	3	4	0	4
5290.26571	1.528E-20	4	0.5037	5	011	1	1	1	2	1	2
5291.7057	3.771E-22	4	0.4467	5	110	2	1	2	1	0	1
5294.38096	3.18E-23	7	0.35	12	011	8	3	6	8	3	5
5299.24815	5.318E-23	12	0.4751	21	110	2	2	1	2	1	2
5299.77866	3.824E-21	4	0.4825	5	011	3	1	3	3	1	2
5304.61825	2.317E-23	7	0.3701	8	110	4	1	3	3	2	2
5305.44026	3.519E-23	6	0.3745	9	110	7	3	4	7	2	5
5306.69388	1.559E-22	4	0.3786	5	110	3	1	3	2	0	2
5307.47285	1.319E-20	4	0.4442	5	011	0	0	0	1	0	1
5308.77318	5.428E-23	7	0.4735	10	110	5	1	4	5	0	5
5311.29161	1.507E-22	5	0.4183	8	110	4	0	4	3	1	3
5314.14582	3.761E-22	4	0.4196	6	011	7	3	5	7	3	4
5314.51814	5.164E-22	4	0.413	6	110	5	3	2	5	2	3
5315.17113	2.095E-23	11	0.4114	22	110	7	2	5	7	1	6
5316.23517	2.554E-21	4	0.4664	5	011	2	1	2	2	1	1
5316.82511	4.804E-23	12	0.4438	21	110	4	2	3	4	1	4
5317.61218	6.256E-22	5	0.4174	6	011	4	2	3	4	2	2
5317.96819*	4.894E-23	11	0.4522	22	011	4	2	0	2	2	1
5320.60798	5.401E-22	4	0.5091	6	110	4	1	4	3	0	3
5322.60573	2.354E-23	13	0.4076	28	021**	2	0	2	1	0	1
5323.95102	9.331E-22	4	0.4335	6	110	4	3	1	4	2	2
5326.64573	1.584E-21	4	0.4213	5	110	3	3	0	3	2	1
5327.39035	1.772E-20	4	0.4635	5	011	1	1	1	1	1	0
5327.64867	3.796E-23	11	0.3612	15	011	3	2	1	4	0	4
5327.67812	8.517E-23	10	0.5103	12	011	4	2	2	5	0	5
5327.96426*	1.897E-23	12	0.4776	20	011	2	1	1	2	1	2
5328.11315	4.974E-23	7	0.3675	12	011	4	3	1	5	1	4
5328.63076	3.99E-22	4	0.4358	6	011	6	3	4	6	3	3
5329.99581	4.599E-22	5	0.4282	6	110	5	0	5	4	1	4
5330.47021	3.389E-23	10	0.5363	15	011	3	0	3	2	2	0
5332.09219	9.546E-21	4	0.4395	5	011	3	2	2	3	2	1
5332.95038	7.541E-23	11	0.395	21	110	3	3	1	3	2	2
5333.7588	9.682E-23	9	0.4189	16	110	5	1	4	4	2	3
5334.63177	1.624E-22	7	0.4235	13	110	5	1	5	4	0	4
5336.18699	8.115E-21	4	0.426	5	011	2	2	1	2	2	0
5336.37279	3.209E-22	6	0.5188	9	110	2	2	1	1	1	0
5336.89441	1.313E-22	9	0.535	15	011	2	2	0	3	0	3
5337.6996	3.353E-21	4	0.4161	6	011	5	3	3	5	3	2
5338.22621	6.103E-21	4	0.4315	5	011	1	1	0	1	1	1
5338.5148	1.091E-22	12	0.5463	19	011	4	0	4	3	2	1
5338.75442	2.461E-20	5	0.4442	6	011	2	2	0	2	2	1
5339.38975	5.66E-23	17	0.4352	37	011	8	4	5	8	4	4
5342.41234	2.777E-21	5	0.3708	6	011	4	3	2	4	3	1
5342.80177	1.029E-22	11	0.444	22	110	2	2	0	1	1	1
5343.4	3.71E-21	4	0.4144	6	011	3	2	1	3	2	2
5344.52449	1.803E-20	4	0.3643	5	011	3	3	1	3	3	0
5344.92316	5.985E-21	4	0.3473	6	011	3	3	0	3	3	1
5345.05378	8.371E-21	5	0.3423	6	011	4	3	1	4	3	2
5346.62584	5.415E-22	5	0.3639	7	011	7	4	4	7	4	3
5346.83294	1.313E-22	5	0.3756	9	110	6	0	6	5	1	5
5347.30036	1.127E-21	4	0.3778	6	011	5	3	2	5	3	3

5348.6754	8.346E-21	4	0.4576	5	011	2	1	1	2	1	2
5348.96147	4.059E-22	5	0.4097	8	110	6	1	6	5	0	5
5350.53402	5.406E-22	4	0.358	5	011	6	4	3	6	4	2
5351.00768	4.478E-23	5	0.416	7	110	7	4	3	7	3	4
5352.61136	1.658E-21	4	0.42	5	011	6	4	2	6	4	3
5352.6224	4.115E-21	4	0.4291	5	011	5	4	2	5	4	1
5352.66374	5.285E-21	4	0.4389	5	011	4	2	2	4	2	3
5353.06962	1.355E-21	4	0.312	5	011	5	4	1	5	4	2
5353.31199	1.187E-21	5	0.4067	7	011	6	3	3	6	3	4
5353.48961	1.911E-22	8	0.3542	17	011	7	4	3	7	4	4
5353.86784	2.949E-21	5	0.2745	6	011	4	4	1	4	4	0
5353.92018	8.755E-21	5	0.2939	6	011	4	4	0	4	4	1
5354.87086	4.795E-21	4	0.4382	6	011	1	0	1	0	0	0
5356.01247*	4.568E-23	7	0.3737	13	011	2	0	2	1	0	1
5357.18372	1.738E-22	5	0.3671	7	011	8	4	4	8	4	5
5359.35249	5.247E-23	5	0.2924	12	011	8	5	4	8	5	3
5360.02189	2.084E-23	10	0.3625	22	021**	4	0	4	3	0	3
5360.58271	2.779E-23	10	0.3272	19	110	6	1	5	5	2	4
5360.8022	1.593E-22	5	0.2736	8	011	8	5	3	8	5	4
5361.23553	3.348E-23	12	0.3852	27	110	6	4	2	6	3	3
5361.52434	4.637E-22	5	0.2627	6	011	7	5	3	7	5	2
5361.89275	1.555E-22	5	0.2547	11	011	7	5	2	7	5	3
5362.36114	2.894E-22	7	0.3734	6	110	7	0	7	6	1	6
5363.04935	4.231E-22	4	0.232	6	011	6	5	2	6	5	1
5363.11566	1.273E-21	4	0.2389	6	011	6	5	1	6	5	2
5363.27808	9.802E-23	7	0.3899	13	110	7	1	7	6	0	6
5364.0327	1.451E-21	4	0.4676	6	011	3	1	2	3	1	3
5364.22047	3.143E-21	5	0.2118	7	011	5	5	1	5	5	0
5364.22687	1.047E-21	5	0.2769	12	011	5	5	0	5	5	1
5364.92948*	3.274E-23	18	0.3943	42	011	2	1	1	1	1	0
5365.9343	3.04E-23	10	0.3698	22	011	6	1	5	5	3	2
5367.19425	7.4E-22	4	0.4507	6	011	5	2	3	5	2	4
5368.29769	3.107E-22	5	0.4744	6	110	4	2	3	3	1	2
5368.58083	1.792E-22	5	0.4007	8	110	5	4	1	5	3	2
5372.28145	3.513E-23	7	0.2296	15	011	8	6	3	8	6	2
5372.34067	1.039E-22	6	0.2246	12	011	8	6	2	8	6	3
5372.68963*	4.504E-23	9	0.4119	17	011	3	1	3	2	1	2
5372.82432	6.417E-23	6	0.39	9	110	4	4	0	4	3	1
5373.3588	7.995E-23	7	0.4156	12	110	5	4	2	5	3	3
5373.56724	2.03E-22	5	0.4011	8	110	6	4	3	6	3	4
5373.77403	3.067E-22	6	0.1985	9	011	7	6	2	7	6	1
5373.7834	1.034E-22	6	0.235	12	011	7	6	1	7	6	2
5374.14157	2.052E-22	5	0.3558	8	110	4	4	1	4	3	2
5374.27398	5.886E-21	4	0.5192	5	011	2	1	2	1	1	1
5374.99887	8.331E-22	5	0.1171	5	011	6	6	0	6	6	1
5374.99806	2.777E-22	5	0.4067	61	011	6	6	1	6	6	0
5375.09981	5.86E-22	5	0.4985	7	110	3	2	1	2	1	2
5376.66675	7.953E-23	11	0.4774	22	110	7	4	4	7	3	5
5376.9424	2.47E-20	5	0.4389	6	011	2	0	2	1	0	1
5377.27559	1.773E-22	6	0.2954	14	110	8	1	8	7	0	7
5380.29996	8.311E-23	12	0.5029	21	110	5	2	4	4	1	3
5382.06492	1.863E-23	19	0.4038	42	021**	4	1	3	3	1	2
5383.44714	2.419E-21	4	0.5022	5	011	4	1	3	4	1	4
5384.1257	8.078E-23	8	0.3733	15	110	7	1	6	6	2	5
5385.80004	1.762E-20	7	0.4149	9	011	2	1	1	1	1	0
5386.42485	9.376E-22	4	0.4545	5	011	6	2	4	6	2	5
5388.12828	1.363E-22	5	0.3721	8	011	8	3	5	8	3	6
5390.55797	1.061E-22	8	0.2869	7	110	9	0	9	8	1	8
5390.78386	3.561E-23	8	0.2863	20	110	9	1	9	8	0	8
5391.05326	1.734E-22	7	0.4185	12	110	6	2	5	5	1	4
5392.7491*	4.916E-23	13	0.416	26	011	4	0	4	3	0	3
5393.64808	2.597E-20	5	0.4689	6	011	3	1	3	2	1	2
5396.54332	9.794E-21	4	0.4649	5	011	3	0	3	2	0	2
5402.04044	2.382E-22	7	0.481	11	110	3	3	0	3	0	3
5402.2601	2.083E-22	5	0.4375	7	011	2	2	1	2	0	2
5403.08789	3.909E-22	4	0.4409	6	110	3	3	1	2	2	0
5403.59593	2.125E-23	8	0.2816	15	110	10	0	10	9	1	9
5403.74207	5.685E-23	6	0.2447	11	110	10	1	10	9	0	9
5403.90045	3.496E-21	4	0.4513	5	110	3	3	0	2	2	1
5405.29027	4.564E-22	4	0.4647	5	011	5	1	4	5	1	5
5407.4869	1.091E-21	4	0.4738	5	011	3	2	2	3	0	3
5407.6314 *	4.956E-23	17	0.5328	9	011	5	1	5	4	1	4
5408.32196	1.619E-23	7	0.4742	10	011	9	3	6	9	3	7
5409.02584	1.304E-22	11	0.4284	21	011	7	2	5	7	2	6
5409.34691	8.688E-21	4	0.4668	6	011	3	2	2	2	2	1
5410.69831	7.177E-21	4	0.4559	6	011	4	1	4	3	1	3
5411.13525	7.836E-21	4	0.4172	6	011	3	1	2	2	1	1
5411.33896	2.258E-22	6	0.4075	11	011	4	2	3	4	0	4
5413.53751	3.652E-21	4	0.4423	5	011	3	2	1	2	2	0
5413.90951	2.783E-20	5	0.4997	6	011	4	0	4	3	0	3
5415.5729	1.456E-21	4	0.4323	5	110	4	2	2	3	1	3
5416.24028	3.623E-23	19	0.2669	32	110	5	5	0	5	4	1
5417.6778	2.437E-22	5	0.4375	6	110	4	3	1	4	0	4
5420.07945*	3.008E-23	11	0.4384	15	011	4	2	2	3	2	1
5422.2576	3.369E-23	8	0.3499	15	110	9	1	8	8	2	7
5422.85767	9.232E-22	4	0.4371	5	110	4	3	2	3	2	1
5424.31473	9.208E-22	4	0.4259	5	011	5	2	4	5	0	5

5424.4787 *	3.64E-23	7	0.479	17	011	6	0	6	5	0	5
5427.09029	2.991E-21	4	0.4204	6	011	4	2	3	3	2	2
5427.494	7.331E-22	5	0.3989	8	011	6	1	5	6	1	6
5428.72533	2.186E-20	4	0.4529	5	011	5	1	5	4	1	4
5430.08702	7.456E-21	4	0.4663	5	011	5	0	5	4	0	4
5433.11645	1.514E-22	7	0.3794	14	011	8	2	6	8	2	7
5433.42913	2.034E-21	4	0.4161	6	110	4	3	1	3	2	2
5434.91972	2.171E-20	6	0.4734	8	011	4	1	3	3	1	2
5435.68091	1.731E-22	5	0.4213	7	110	5	3	2	5	0	5
5438.96312	1.657E-22	5	0.4481	7	110	5	3	3	4	2	2
5439.03881	2.18E-22	5	0.3815	7	011	6	2	5	6	0	6
5439.42526*	2.176E-23	24	0.3559	14	011	7	1	7	6	1	6
5440.86966	1.447E-20	6	0.4021	8	011	4	2	2	3	2	1
5441.03551	1.97E-21	4	0.395	6	011	4	3	2	3	3	1
5442.15209	5.968E-21	4	0.3829	6	011	4	3	1	3	3	0
5445.09077	5.322E-21	6	0.4006	5	011	6	1	6	5	1	5
5445.72615	1.608E-20	6	0.4276	8	011	6	0	6	5	0	5
5447.05414	4.134E-22	6	0.4354	9	011	5	3	3	5	1	4
5447.27389	1.266E-22	10	0.4537	17	011	6	3	4	6	1	5
5448.51018	1.241E-22	8	0.3627	16	011	7	1	6	7	1	7
5449.30035	1.21E-20	5	0.4363	6	011	5	2	4	4	2	3
5449.86171	4.563E-22	5	0.4663	8	011	2	2	0	1	0	1
5450.75782	1.081E-22	9	0.4741	17	011	4	3	2	4	1	3
5451.29075	2.342E-22	6	0.4501	11	110	6	3	4	5	2	3
5452.28836	2.395E-22	4	0.3889	5	011	7	3	5	7	1	6
5454.82765	3.63E-22	4	0.3462	5	011	7	2	6	7	0	7
5456.41869	5.583E-21	4	0.4645	5	011	5	1	4	4	1	3
5456.70787	1.759E-23	6	0.3237	11	011	9	2	7	9	2	8
5460.66308	1.029E-20	4	0.3609	5	011	7	1	7	6	1	6
5460.93949	3.444E-21	4	0.3786	5	011	7	0	7	6	0	6
5461.34168	3.07E-23	34	0.423	67	110	5	2	3	4	1	4
5461.6483	4.599E-23	18	0.4411	39	011	8	3	6	8	1	7
5463.99477	6.594E-21	4	0.3891	5	011	5	3	3	4	3	2
5467.42594	2.19E-21	4	0.3452	6	011	5	3	2	4	3	1
5467.62345	4.067E-21	4	0.405	5	011	5	2	3	4	2	2
5467.87668	1.665E-22	10	0.2791	9	011	8	1	7	8	1	8
5468.14469	3.914E-23	14	0.3769	33	110	8	3	6	7	2	5
5469.52667	3.058E-21	4	0.4297	5	011	6	2	5	5	2	4
5471.09889	5.475E-23	10	0.2769	30	011	8	2	7	8	0	8
5474.11876	5.037E-23	11	0.2798	33	011	9	3	7	9	1	8
5474.85587	2.168E-21	5	0.3129	6	011	5	4	2	4	4	1
5475.04988	7.228E-22	5	0.3065	7	011	5	4	1	4	4	0
5475.28884	1.093E-20	5	0.4432	6	011	6	1	5	5	1	4
5475.56096	1.958E-21	4	0.3353	6	011	8	1	8	7	1	7
5475.67563	5.894E-21	4	0.3356	6	011	8	0	8	7	0	7
5479.61062	2.762E-22	5	0.4043	7	011	3	2	1	2	0	2
5485.60933	2.23E-23	15	0.392	33	011	9	4	6	9	2	7
5485.81265	2.564E-23	8	0.2919	20	011	9	1	8	9	1	9
5486.21157	1.668E-21	4	0.3842	5	011	6	3	4	5	3	3
5487.33529	7.587E-23	7	0.2907	16	011	9	2	8	9	0	9
5488.1598	5.609E-21	4	0.385	6	011	7	2	6	6	2	5
5489.8424	3.065E-21	5	0.2743	6	011	9	1	9	8	1	8
5489.88483	1.023E-21	5	0.2672	8	011	9	0	9	8	0	8
5492.08359	2.035E-21	4	0.4251	6	011	7	1	6	6	1	5
5492.82557	8.215E-21	4	0.4056	6	011	6	2	4	5	2	3
5493.47863	4.854E-21	4	0.3743	6	011	6	3	3	5	3	2
5494.11082	5.291E-23	16	0.3441	40	110	6	3	3	5	2	4
5495.45312	6.237E-23	10	0.4064	20	011	7	4	4	7	2	5
5498.19978	7.324E-22	4	0.3185	6	011	6	4	3	5	4	2
5498.99498	2.197E-21	4	0.3222	6	011	6	4	2	5	4	1
5502.73228	7.717E-23	9	0.447	17	011	4	3	1	4	1	4
5503.51043	4.711E-22	4	0.2501	8	011	10	1	10	9	1	9
5503.54107	1.417E-21	4	0.2421	7	011	10	0	10	9	0	9
5505.55433	1.013E-21	4	0.3364	6	011	8	2	7	7	2	6
5507.52371	3.122E-21	4	0.3818	6	011	7	3	5	6	3	4
5507.8253	3.167E-21	4	0.3694	6	011	8	1	7	7	1	6
5509.60898	2.035E-22	5	0.2787	8	011	6	5	2	5	5	1
5509.63811	6.134E-22	5	0.2673	7	011	6	5	1	5	5	0
5513.73388	2.623E-22	5	0.3878	8	110	6	4	3	5	3	2
5515.86056	1.515E-21	4	0.4341	6	011	7	2	5	6	2	4
5516.26437	7.639E-22	4	0.4719	6	011	4	2	2	3	0	3
5516.45289	6.439E-23	8	0.4459	14	011	5	4	2	5	2	3
5516.61943	6.013E-22	5	0.2181	7	011	11	1	11	10	1	10
5516.63487	2.01E-22	5	0.2619	11	011	11	0	11	10	0	10
5518.28686	7.65E-22	4	0.3748	6	011	7	3	4	6	3	3
5518.81634	2.398E-23	12	0.3446	31	110	6	4	2	5	3	3
5521.13816	1.472E-21	5	0.3123	6	011	7	4	4	6	4	3
5521.90343	1.413E-21	5	0.2834	6	011	9	2	8	8	2	7
5523.13237	4.941E-22	5	0.3185	8	011	9	1	8	8	1	7
5523.45332	5.034E-22	5	0.3481	8	011	7	4	3	6	4	2
5527.84439	5.373E-22	4	0.3361	6	011	8	3	6	7	3	5
5529.15397	7.572E-23	5	0.192	19	011	12	1	12	11	1	11
5529.16755	2.267E-22	5	0.1912	10	011	12	0	12	11	0	11
5531.81208	2.572E-22	5	0.4037	7	110	7	4	4	6	3	3
5532.76104	5.487E-22	5	0.2648	6	011	7	5	3	6	5	2
5532.90675	1.829E-22	5	0.2586	9	011	7	5	2	6	5	1
5534.96657	6.998E-23	9	0.46	12	011	3	3	0	2	1	1

5535.66144	3.814E-22	5	0.4102	7	110	8	4	5	7	3	4
5536.30684	2.132E-21	4	0.4129	6	011	8	2	6	7	2	5
5537.54109	2.037E-22	4	0.2499	8	011	10	2	9	9	2	8
5538.12874	6.185E-22	4	0.2562	7	011	10	1	9	9	1	8
5541.1473	8.429E-23	15	0.2099	15	011	13	1	13	12	1	12
5541.66559	2.309E-23	9	0.3001	22	011	4	4	0	4	2	3
5543.42142	2.666E-22	4	0.3049	7	011	8	4	5	7	4	4
5544.38557	5.216E-23	6	0.3074	12	110	7	4	3	6	3	4
5544.61693	1.768E-23	11	0.3799	24	110	9	4	6	8	3	5
5544.91059	1.314E-22	8	0.1704	18	011	7	6	2	6	6	1
5544.91483	4.38E-23	8	0.3017	46	011	7	6	1	6	6	0
5547.0824	7.476E-22	4	0.3271	6	011	9	3	7	8	3	6
5548.65515	8.075E-22	4	0.3497	6	011	8	4	4	7	4	3
5550.44668	1.177E-22	6	0.4365	10	011	3	3	1	2	1	2
5551.88762	1.154E-21	4	0.4051	6	011	8	3	5	7	3	4
5552.47274	2.436E-22	6	0.2411	7	011	11	2	10	10	2	9
5552.76082	7.953E-23	6	0.2262	16	011	11	1	10	10	1	9
5554.18159	2.829E-22	6	0.3828	8	011	9	2	7	8	2	6
5554.20486	3.888E-22	6	0.4682	7	011	4	3	1	3	1	2
5555.61738	1.134E-22	4	0.2783	7	011	8	5	4	7	5	3
5556.13351	3.402E-22	4	0.2812	6	011	8	5	3	7	5	2
5556.42476	3.282E-23	10	0.2984	18	011	6	4	2	6	2	5
5561.35023	1.475E-22	5	0.5085	8	011	5	2	3	4	0	4
5564.8223	3.786E-22	4	0.3248	6	011	9	4	6	8	4	5
5565.17473	9.99E-23	5	0.2869	9	011	10	3	8	9	3	7
5566.81593	2.799E-23	7	0.2209	14	011	12	2	11	11	2	10
5566.97447	8.404E-23	5	0.1973	12	011	12	1	11	11	1	10
5567.73357	3.837E-23	5	0.2826	9	011	8	6	3	7	6	2
5567.7576	1.135E-22	4	0.2765	5	011	8	6	2	7	6	1
5570.1837	3.42E-22	4	0.3643	5	011	10	2	8	9	2	7
5574.32072	1.214E-22	6	0.3076	10	011	9	4	5	8	4	4
5574.39555	2.036E-22	5	0.4105	8	011	9	3	6	8	3	5
5575.77141	1.554E-22	5	0.4472	8	011	5	3	2	4	1	3
5578.03863	1.525E-22	7	0.2396	7	011	9	5	5	8	5	4
5579.47738	5.094E-23	7	0.2619	17	011	9	5	4	8	5	3
5580.6288	2.424E-23	13	0.1476	17	011	13	2	12	12	2	11
5582.16676	1.075E-22	7	0.2741	7	011	11	3	9	10	3	8
5583.97637	5.603E-23	6	0.3996	10	011	4	3	2	3	1	3
5585.2027	5.237E-23	6	0.3421	12	011	10	4	7	9	4	6
5585.25601	3.819E-23	8	0.3366	14	011	11	2	9	10	2	8

V' - upper state vibrational index

J' Ka' Kc' and J'' Ka'' Kc'' - upper and lower state rotational indices respectively.

* H₂¹⁸O lines

** V''=010 (otherwise V''=000)

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

